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THE USE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH LESSONS FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract: the article defines that usage of modern information technology in the development of students' lexical competence in English lessons for medical students. Moreover there are given many ways based on conducting the lesson through IT technology.

Key words: teaching languages, language learning, computer assisted vocabulary learning, lexical competence, vocabulary studying.

Grammatical and phonological structures together with the constant repetition of sentence patterns were among the primary issues of teaching languages at that time. It was thought that learning lexical items could be delayed until one could gain enough competence in the structure of a language. However, this did not last long. After the focus of language learning moved from the structural patterns to meaningful communication in the 1970s with Hyme's (1972) communicative competence concept, interest in learning and teaching vocabulary gradually increased. For the last three decades, with the advent of communicative language teaching and computer assisted language learning (CALL), more studies concerning vocabulary learning and teaching have appeared. With the increase in research with regard to vocabulary learning and teaching, new ways, strategies, and methods have emerged. Some of these strategies include guessing meaning from context, using mnemonic devices, employing vocabulary notebooks, teaching word origins and structural analysis, using semantic mapping, showing students how to attack analogies, reading aloud, dramatization, showing students how to use the dictionary, using cloze sentences, benefiting from L1 cognates and so on. The fact that vocabulary knowledge involves more than learning the words in isolation has led to the emergence of corpus-based studies, using collocations and semantic associations, and finally Lewis's (1993) Lexical Approach in which learning chunks of language is attached primary importance. Lexical Approach puts lexis at the center of language and advocates that grammatical mastery is not a requirement for effective communication. Lewis (1993) points out that language curriculum should be organized on the basis of lexis rather than grammar.

Lewis's remarks on the importance of lexis in language learning and teaching emphasize the need of vocabulary instruction in classes. In the current literature, vocabulary instruction can be categorized as implicit and explicit. Implicit vocabulary learning occurs when the mind focuses on elsewhere such as on understanding a text or using language for communicative purposes. Words can be acquired naturally through various sources and activities which are mainly communicative and meaningful. On the other hand, explicit vocabulary learning is supported by researchers who think that vocabulary items should be taught explicitly by means of different strategies. They argue that both vocabulary and vocabulary learning strategies need to be taught explicitly. Considering these two distinct approaches, it is not possible to mention one of them as thoroughly true or false. It is a stubborn fact that both implicit and explicit vocabulary learning strategies have been employed in language learning and teaching context so far. That is, the color of the area that should be focused on by language teachers is grey rather than black or white. Foreign language teachers may benefit from both strategy types in accordance with the needs of the learners. One of the ways of adopting this eclectic vocabulary instruction type is computer assisted vocabulary learning which has been very popular in recent years. It is time at this point to have a close look at the related research on computer assisted vocabulary learning.

Relevant Studies on Computer Assisted Vocabulary Learning CALL and computer vocabulary learning in particular have attracted a great deal of attention in the field of language learning and teaching especially in recent years. A number of studies have been conducted to examine the effectiveness of CALL in vocabulary studies. The studies in the present literature generally reveal positive findings about both the achievement and attitude aspects of computer assisted vocabulary learning. To start with the recent studies in the literature, Li's (2010) study which investigates ESL learners' vocabulary learning outcomes through reading reveals that the students learned more words with access to computer-mediated dictionaries than those without. Another research yielding findings in favor of computer assisted vocabulary learning is administered by Lin, Chan and Hsiao.

All in all, the study attempts to explore EFL students' perceptions of learning vocabulary collaboratively with computers. 91 students are assigned to the three different learning environments; learning individually without computers, learning collaboratively without computers and learning collaboratively with computers. The results show that more than 70% of the

participants in the computer group report positive attitudes towards learning vocabulary through computers.

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